

GEOGRAPHY

**Role of Sugar Factory in Rural Development: A Case Study of
Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana,
Venunagar – Pandharpur**

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ABSTRACT:

Sugarcane is transforming life of Maharashtra's rural folk. From agriculture to political sugar industry playing very active role and its called institutions to rural upliftment. Irrigation facilities assured market for sugarcane assured cash return to farmers which has supported to improve the economic status of the farmers in several ways. E.g. Housing status, status of domestic material, status of house hold vehicles etc. For the present study Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana, Venunagar – Pandharpur and its command area is selected for its detailed study.

Sugarcane cultivation is the base of sugar factory which provides raw material. Sugar factories are giving inputs in various forms for the development of surrounding rural area. Here attempt has been made to take the review of role of Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana, Venunagar – Pandharpur in the development of status of sugarcane farmers.

For this study data & information is collected through intensive field work. It is supplimentary by secondary sources of data collected from districts statistical abstract and gazettes. Collected data is processed and presented in tabular and diagramic form. From this study it is found that there is positive impact of Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana, Venunagar – Pandharpur on the improvement of status farmers and farming practices.

Key words –

Co-Operative Sugar Factory, Rural Development, Social and Economical Change

INTRODUCTION:

Sugar industry is most important source of income in agriculture sector. In India sugar industry has an importance of other industries in India. Sugarcane is transforming life of Maharashtra rural life from agriculture to political sugar industry playing a vital role in rural life platforms.

Sugarcane cultivation is the base of sugar factory which provides raw material. Sugar factories are giving inputs in various forms for the development of surrounding rural area. Here attempt has been made to take the review of role of Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana, Venunagar – Pandharpur in the development of status of sugarcane farmers.

STUDY AREA:

The selected region for the present study is venunagar_Gursale village, which is located in pandharpur tashil is situated in the extreme southern part of Maharashtra state. Especially pandharpur tashil is located central part of solapur district. It lies between coordinate 17 40 30 north latitude and 75 19 36 east longitudes cover an area of 1303 sq.km and nature of are mostly lies rural. These tashil bounded by Madha to North, mohol to the North- East , Songola and mangalwedha lies respectively to south East and south west.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To find the status and historical background of Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana, Gursale
2. To Analyse the social and economical change among sugarcane growers.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY:

The information and data are the most important for research, without proper information and data, research cannot be carried out. No desirable conclusion and generalization may be obtained without proper data analyses. Hence, the data that is basic tools of the research is collected from different sources such as published and unpublished works, Reports and census of Government. Publication have used for the analysis purpose. With the help of an interview, the first hand data is collected and results are interpreted accordingly. The present study relies upon primary data the represented data is interpreted and analysed to find the desirable results and conclusion.

HISTORICAL REVIEW OF SUGAR FACTORY:

In the year 1973 Shri. Vitthal S.S.K. Venunagar got a industrial registration number. Shir. Audhumbar Patil Popularly known as Anna. With his Collogue registered this sugar factory with the help of late Shri. Yashawantrao Chavan then chief minister of Maharashtra State. On the Barren and rocky land near Pandharpur city is selected for the proposed sugar co-operative factory. Initial two years site selection is not done because of administrative regions. In 10th November 1975 Shri. Audhumbar Anna Patil decided land four sugar co-operative. Latterly in the 1976 foundation stone is landed over sugar factory site on 24th October 1976 by the hands of Yashwantrao Chavan. The Machinery and construction work begin on 1977. The first test of sugarcane crushing is conducted in a year 1979-80. Initially the sugar factory has permission to crush 2000 TCD. The sugar factory has distillery unit since 1985. The capacity of distillery unit is 30000 liters. per day. Improved irrigation facilities and good price for sugarcane results rise in area under sugarcane crop. In 1991 the sugar factory increased its capacity from 2000 TCD to 3500 TCD. This has further increased crushing capacity in a year

1996 by 5000 TCD. Presently this sugar factory has distillery unit, compositing, and co-generation.

Table – 1 Sample design for selection of Village and Households

Name of Village	Number of Samples	Small Farmer	Medium Farmer	Big Farmer
Bhose	12	04	04	04
Gursale	12	04	04	04
Sarkoli	12	04	04	04
Sonake	12	04	04	04
Vakhari	12	04	04	04
Ambe	12	04	04	04
Tungat	12	04	04	04
Bhandishegaon	12	04	04	04
Total	96	32	32	32

Source: Compiled by Researcher

In Pandharpur tahsil irrigation immediately impact on growth of cash crop like sugarcane. Though first sugar factory is open at Malshiras tahsil but sugarcane from Pandharpur tahsil has been provided to this sugar factory. For the present study 8 (eight) villages are selected with strategic sampling. These villages produced more sugarcane are indentified and out of them eight are selected for present research. These villages are Bhose, Gursale, Sarkoli, Sonake, Vakhari, Bhandishegaon, Tungat and Ambe. From each villages 12 samples i.e. sugarcane grower are choose to obtain in depth interview schedule. The location of sugar factory is playing important role during social and economic transformation. In this concern I indentify a some key-results from Gursale, Bhose and Vakhari Villagers. These are directly connected to the Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Venunagar (Pandharpur). All like Sahakar Maharashi Shankarrao Mohite-Patil Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Shankrnagar, Small, medium and big farmers are differentiated. (Please See Table No.1)

Table No.2 Housing Condition of Respondents

Category of Farmers	Number of Facilities in the Group	Year	Pacca		Medium		Kaccha	
				%		%		%
Small Farmers	32	1970-71	00	00	00	00	32	33.33 (100.00)
	32	2010-11	15	15.62 (46.87)	10	10.41 (31.25)	07	7.29 (21.87)
Medium Farmer	32	1970-71	05	5.20 (15.62)	15	(15.62) (46.87)	12	12.50 (37.50)
	32	2010-11	20	20.83 (62.50)	10	10.41 (31.25)	02	2.08 (6.25)
Big Farmer	32	1970-71	15	15.62 (46.87)	05	5.20 (15.62)	12	12.50 (37.50)
	32	2010-11	30	31.25 (93.75)	02	2.08 (6.25)	00	00
Total	96	1970-71	20	20.83	20	20.83	56	58.33
	96	2010-11	65	67.70	22	22.91	09	09.37

Source – Compiled by Researcher

Table 2 Shows condition of the houses of sugarcane grower of Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Venunagar (Pandharpur). In the small farmer category 1970-71 only kaccha houses are observed. This situation has been changed in 2010-11 were 46.87 percent sugarcane grower built pacca houses and 31.25 percent stay in the medium houses. Here define medium houses means roof is iron sheet and walls are built by concrete and mud. This result is showing the picture of economical transformation among the small category sugarcane grower. This is possible by the inputs of co-operative development through sugar factory. During data collection work, I met with small category sugarcane grower Mr. Shankar Bhandare who own 0.8 hectors land and cultivated 0.5 hector sugarcane for last 8 years. He recently built 3 rooms cement concrete with iron sheet roof house. He added that this is only possible because sugarcane and loan from Shri Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Venunagar (Pandharpur).

In the medium category sugarcane grower the housing condition are not so good in the year 1970-71,. Where only 15.65 percent sugarcane grower had pacca house and 46.87 percent had medium house. This situation is changed and other new constructional facilities are also accepted by this category sugarcane grower. In a year 2010-11, the 62.50 percent sugarcane grower had pacca house, while 31.25 percent have medium house, only 6.28 percent sugarcane grower is live in the kaccha house.

In the Big category farmer situation of the housing condition is so strong in the year 2010-11. It is amazing to see that 93.75 percent sugarcane grower are now built big houses. Where as in the year 1970-71 only 46.87 percent big category sugarcane grower had RCC cement concrete house. In this category not only sugarcane grower in the Kaccha house. In the discussion with the big category farmer. I narrate a case study of Mr. Shivajirao Thorat From Sonake has 10 hectors of sugarcane and his home is well furnished which costing 50 Lakh Ruppes. He explain, "after sugar factory we are not imagine to built a big bunglow. But we are much more progressed and staying at well furnished and air condition home. Though some people blaming sugarcane grower for lazy person but we are much more lucky due to economic gains and social upliftment.

In a short its is found that sugarcane grower of Shri Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Venunagar (Pandharpur) having house condition like 67.70 percent stay in the pacca house, 22.90 percent staying in the medium house and 9.37 percent stay in the kaccha house. As compare to the 1970-71 situation 58.33 percent built Pacca House.

Table No.3 (A) Status of Domestic Materials

Category of Farmers	Number of Facilities in the Group	Year	Chair	Percentage	Table	Percentage	Fans	Percentage	Radio	Percentage	T.V.	Percentage
Small Farmers	32	1970-71	0	00	00	00	00	00	09	9.37 (23.12)	00	00
	32	2010-11	30	31.25 (93.75)	15	15.62 (46.87)	20	20.83 (62.50)	27	20.12 (84.37)	31	32.29 (96.87)
Medium Farmer	32	1970-71	00	00	00	00	10	10.41 (31.25)	12	12.5 (37.50)	07	7.29 (21.87)
	32	2010-11	30	31.25 (93.75)	28	29.16 (87.50)	32	33.33 (100.00)	31	32.29 (96.87)	32	33.33 (100.00)
Big Farmer	32	1970-71	04	4.16 (12.50)	02	2.08 (6.25)	09	9.37 (28.12)	10	10.41 (31.25)	07	7.29 (21.87)
	32	2010-11	32	33.33 (100.0)	32	33.33 (100.0)	32	33.33 (100.00)	32	33.33 (100.00)	32	33.33 (100.00)
Total	96	1970-71	04	4.16	02	2.08	19	19.79	31	32.29	14	14.58
	96	2010-11	92	95.83	75	78.12	84	87.5	90	93.75	95	98.95

Source – Compiled by Researcher

Table and Chairs :-

Table 3 (A) Shows the change in the physical asset among sugarcane grower from the period 1970-71 to 2010-11. In the 1970-71 the sugarcane grower didn't have chairs. This situation is drastically change in the year 2010-11 were 93.70 percent small category sugarcane grower have chairs and table respectively. In the medium category sugarcane grower the chair and table in a year 1970-71 is lacking this is changed in the year 2010-11 were 93.70 percent sugarcane grower replies positively that they have chair and 6.25 percent have a table. Now all the big farmer have table and chairs. In a short it is analysed that 4.16 percent and 2.08 percent sugarcane grower had chair and table in the year 1970-71. This is changed in the 2010-11 were 95.83 percent has chair and 72.12 percent has table.

Fan, Radio and Television :-

From the year 1970-71 all there category sugarcane grower using Radio for entertainment and update with news. Though small category farmer have Radio (28.12 Percent) and in the year 2010-11 it is increased upto 83.87 percent. IN medium sugarcane grower 37.50 percent had radio and it is reached to 96.70 percent by the year 2010-11. In the big farmer all has radio in their home in the 2010-11 but 1970-71 this is up to 31.25 percent own radio. Fans generally used for maintaining room temperature and aeration. In the small category sugarcane grower the fans area not observed in the year 1970-71 and now 62.50 percent have it. In the medium category sugarcane grower fans are limited up to 31.25 percent respondents and it is increased by 100 percent. In same trend in the also seen in the big category farmers.

The Television is a fancy item in the year 1970-71 and only few people are afford it. This is clearly seen in the table 6 (A). in the small category sugarcane grower there is no Television in the 1970-71

This is changed in the 2010-11 and Television now available in 96.87 percent homes of the respondents. In the medium category sugarcange grower in the 2010-11. All of them have Television but in past i.e. 1970-71 only 21.87 percent has Television. The same trend is repeated in the Big farmer category.

Overall in this section the rise in the Fan, Radio and Television among the sugarcane grower. The radio rise from the 32.29 to 93.75 percent, fans increased up to 19.79 to 87.50 percent and Television grows to 14.58 to 98.95 percent. In the year 1970-71 to 2010-11. Among all of these popular electrical equipment growth in the Television is keenly seen as a indicator of economical transformation among sugarcane grower.

Freeze and Cooler: -

Freeze and cooler are now a days not expensive electronics items. Farmer of India is not savvy with freeze and coolers but in the globalization era freeze and Coolers are very essential because of Indian climate especially in the summer season. In this study attempt is to find the accessibility of the freeze and by the sugarcane rower in my study area. In Shri Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Venunagar (Pandharpur) the sugarcane grower has valid opinions to have Freeze and Cooler in their homes. In the Small farmer category 1970-71 they didn't have freeze and Coolers. Even in the medium and Big farmer category the freeze and coolers are not observed in the table 3 (B).

This is because of electricity is not reach to villages and there was don't have sugar factory. As first sugarcane crushing season of this sugar factory is start in the year 1985 and then subsequently rise in the economic, educational activities within the command area. In a year 2010-11 the 53.12 percent small category farmer having freeze and 15.62 having coolers. In the medium farmer freeze and coolers are available in the 56.25 percent and 28.12 percent respectively. In the big farmer category the freeze and cooler are observed in 65.62 percent and 75 percent home respectively.

Over the entire rise in the freeze and cooler numbers are very high in the Shri Vitthal Sahakari Sakhar Karkhana Ltd. Venunagar (Pandharpur) Sugarcane growers. In this concern I came into firm result that economical development of the sugarcane grower is chiefly because of sugar co-operative farmer or sugarcane grower enjoying the benefits of sugar co-operatives.

Gas and Washing Machines: -

The liquid petroleum gas that is LPG is very scars in the 1970-71. In these days farmer are using crowding, wood and other agricultural based

resources for cooking. In the sugarcane grower only big farmer have gas accessibility i.e. 6.25 percent. In the small and medium farmer category there was gas connectivity as zero percent. The small farmer category 62.50 percent has gas and in the medium farmer 71.87 percent has gas connection. It is seen that there was tremendous growth of gas connections in the sugarcane growers. Now all the big farmers in my study area have Gas connections. In this context I have you the example of Sarkoli was the entire sugarcane grower have gas in their homes.

Washing Machines – It is pertaining to note that till date small farmer didn't have washing machine in their hams. In the medium and big farmer washing is not observed 1970-71 data and in a year 2010-11 this been rise to 9.37 and 40.62 percent respectively.

Overall washing in the sugarcane grower category are only 16.66 percent upto year 2010-11.

Phone / Cell Phone / Mobile: -

In small farmer category Telephone are doesn't seen in the year 2010-11. But 2010-11 the 90.62 percent sugarcane grower opt mobile phones. In the medium farmer category 28.12 percent had Telephone were as in year 2010-11 this number is rise up to 93.75 percent. The big farmer category in 1970-71 Telephone is used by 21.87 percent while in a year 2010-11 all the sugarcane grower using mobile phones. Tough the mobile phones are communicating but it is also useful for tracking the sugarcane cutting schedule total sugarcane weight and payment details. These observations are come forward during discussion the sugarcane grower.

In a short rise in the Telephone use is grown from the 16.66 percent ot 94.79 percent In the four decades.

Table No. 3 (C) Status of Vehicles own by the sugarcane Grower

Category Of Farmers	Number of Facilities in the Group	Year	2 Wheeler	Percentage	2 Wheeler	Percentage
Small Farmer	32	1970-71	00	00	00	00
	32	2010-11	24	25.00 (75.00)	03	3.12 (9.37)
Medium Farmer	32	1970-71	05	5.20 (15.62)	02	2.08 (6.25)
	32	2010-11	29	30.20 (90.62)	09	9.37 (28.12)
Big Farmer	32	1970-71	07	7.29 (21.87)	04	4.16 (12.50)
	32	2010-11	30	31.25 (93.25)	19	19.79 (59.37)
Total	96	1970-71	12	12.50	06	6.258
	96	2010-11	83	86.45	31	32.29

In the year 1970-71 the small farmers don't have two wheeler and four wheelers. This situation is no longer to 2010-11. The status of two wheeler own by 75.00 percent sugarcane grower and 9.37 percent sugarcane grower as four wheeler vehicles. This number is rise upto 90.62 percent and 28.12 percent respectively. In the big farmer situation of two wheeler vehicles and four wheeler vehicles is good in the year 1970-71. Basically majority of big farmer are landlord and they keeping their ancestor's asset. Therefore they maintain four wheeler vehicles and it is the status symbol to show his leadership in the big farmer category rise from 21.87 percent to 93.75 percent and four wheeler vehicles rise from 12.5 percent to 5937 percent. Overall two wheeler vehicles in the sugarcane grower rise from 12.50 percent of 86.45 percent and four wheeler vehicles in this group are rise from 6.25 percent to 32.29 percent.

CONCLUSION:

Overall the study of Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sugar factory and its command area highlight the following conclusion –

1. The growth and development of Vitthal sugar factory since last two decades has helped to do the development in its command areas.
2. Vitthal sahakari sugar factory has made comfortable living of the ordinary farmers by providing well equipped standard of living.
3. Since last 5 – six years it is observed that farmers from the command area are very well progressed and developed which is keenly indicating not only economical but social, educational and agricultural growth in condition.
4. Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sugar factory not only helped in the growth of financial condition of the command area but also improved the irrigated command area by creating awareness among the farmers of as section about the exact need of present.
5. In short, the sugar factory and its command areas leading towards high growth and developed in field area.

SUGGESTIONS:

As the Shri. Vitthal Sahakari Sugar factory proved its existence by developing their command area but still I think there are very few area where we need to think over it. They are as follows –

1. The growth and development of farmers in some sections is not satisfactory, especially the medium farmers where there is a large huge scope to improve with their living styles.
2. Even though the development in economical condition is good but still it is observed that the family right from big to medium are not that much literate which they should be so the sugar factory should bad with this short wining have stepped up with some successive decisions

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can give huge stress as the education by providing some facilities such as free schooling, education in the region.

3. The basic facilities that have been provided by sugar factory through various financial aspects like advance payment. Loose etc. need the great support of irrigation system and improvement in the availability of good quality seeds, pesticides, insecticides etc. In and around the command area which will help to increase the production of sugarcane.
4. All together the factory has lead to love a standard life to the farmers in its areas with its co-operative recommendations.

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